

Relationship between leaf chlorophyll content and rice yield. Beaumont, Texas.

Chlorophyll reading	Expected yield increase (t/ha)	Expected net return to topdressing N (\$)
20	1.4	93
30	0.7	37
35	0.4	17
40	0.1	(-3)

topdressed with 45 kg/ha 2 wk before and at panicle differentiation. Net income due to topdressing decreased as leaf chlorophyll increased.

When chlorophyll readings were near 39 and higher, there was no economic advantage to topdressing N (assuming urea = \$165/t, application cost = \$8.64/ha, and rice value = \$8/cwt).

The chlorophyll meter (model SPAD-501 developed by Minolta) does have limitations: initial cost = \$1400. But fertilizing a 40-ha field with 45 kg N/ha also = approximately \$1400. Another limiting factor is that leaf chlorophyll can be influenced by P, Zn, and Fe deficiencies; low temperature; rice variety; growth stage; and herbicides. □

Economy in combining fertilizer N with green manure in lowland rice

G. Shukla, P. C. Pandey, P. S. Bisht, and P. Lal, Agronomy Department, G.B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar, Nainital 263145, Uttar Pradesh, India

We studied the integrated effect of organic + inorganic N on rice yield and N use efficiency and recovery during wet season 1988. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. The soil is silt loam classed as Aquic Hapludoll, with pH 7.9, 1.1% organic C, CEC 20 meq/100 g, and 0.1% total N.

For green manure, 50-d-old crops of *Sesbania rostrata* and *S. aculeata* were chopped and incorporated into the top 15 cm soil at 10 and 20 t/ha, respectively, 1 wk before transplanting. Farmyard manure (FYM), 20 t/ha fresh weight basis, was incorporated 1 mo before transplanting. Pant Dhan 4 was sown 1 Jun and transplanted 11 Jul. All plots received 17.6 kg P, 24.2 kg K, 10 kg Zn/ha before transplanting. N was applied per treatment (see table).

Yield with *Sesbania* alone equaled yield with 90 kg N as prilled urea (PU). *Sesbania* with 30 kg N as PU increased the grain yield 9%, which was significantly higher than that with 90 kg N as PU alone and equaled yield with 120 kg N as PU or USG.

Highest N use efficiency and apparent N recovery was with *Sesbania* alone.

S. rostrata proved no better than *S. aculeata*, probably because it had only half the biomass. □

Effect of organic and inorganic N source on yield, N uptake, N use efficiency, and apparent N recovery in rice.^a Pantnagar, India, 1988.

Treatment	Time and rate of N			Grain yield (t/ha)	N uptake (kg/ha)			N use efficiency (kg grain/kg N applied)	Apparent N recovery (%)	
	Basal through	PU			Total N (kg/ha)	Grain	Straw			Total
		6-7	DBPI							
	GM	PU								
Control	0	0	0	0	3.8	54	24	78	-	
USG	0	80	40	120	5.8	95	61	156	17	
PU	0	80	40	120	5.7	93	46	139	16	
PU	0	50	40	90	5.4	82	51	133	18	
SA ^b + PU	60	20	40	120	6.1	101	55	155	19	
SR ^b + PU	40	40	40	120	6.1	100	55	155	19	
FYM ^b + PU	50	30	40	120	6.1	100	45	145	19	
SA + PU	60	30	0	90	6.0	100	44	144	24	
SR + PU	40	30	0	70	5.8	96	42	138	29	
FYM + PU	50	30	30	110	5.0	77	38	118	11	
SA	60	0	0	60	5.3	87	46	113	25	
SR	40	0	0	40	5.2	75	33	108	38	
LSD (0.05)					0.4	6	7	11	-	

^aGM = green manure, USG = urea supergranule (46% N), PU = prilled urea (46% N), SA = *Sesbania aculeata* (2% N, 80% moisture), SR = *Sesbania rostrata* (1.75% N, 83% moisture), FYM = farmyard manure (0.5% N, 50% moisture). ^bN content in sesbania and FYM was analyzed, The remaining N was applied through PU to meet the basal requirement of 80 kg N/ha. The rest or 1/3 of 120 kg N was applied at 6-7 d before panicle initiation (DBPI).

Effect of deep-placed urea supergranules (USG) with limited green manure on transplanted rice yield

S. S. Dhane, R. R. Khadse, and V. H. Patil, Regional Agricultural Research Station (RARS), Konkan Krishi Vidyapeeth (KKV), Karjat, Maharashtra State 410201, India; and N. K. Savant, International Fertilizer Development Center (IFDC), P. O. Box 2040, Muscle Shoals, Alabama 35662, USA

The amount of green manure available in small rainfed rice farmers' fields is likely to be very limited. In 1988 wet season, we compared the effect of deep-placed USG and split-applied prilled

urea (PU) alone and in combination with limited amounts of *Gliricidia sepium* leaves on rainfed transplanted rice.

The 11 treatments were laid out in 15-m² plots on the RARS farm, Karjat, in a randomized block design with three replications. Soil was clay loam with pH (1:2.5 soil:water) 7.0 and cation exchange capacity 30 meq/100 g. All plots received 17 kg P/ha as single superphosphate and 33 kg K/ha as potassium chloride.

PU (38 kg N/ha) was applied 50% broadcast and incorporated before transplanting and 50% topdressed before panicle initiation. USG (1-g pellets) was hand placed about 10 cm deep during